

A STUDY FOCUS ON PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS FACED BY WOMEN EMPLOYEES IN GARMENT COMPANIES IN TIRUPUR CITY

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Abstract

Women's income generates even the country's net national product. These researchers are looking into how women in the clothing business might better use their legal rights in that sector. The significant level of female participation in this industry, particularly in Tirupur, makes it a good pick. An investigation into women's rights in the garment sector near Tirupur is conducted here. During the study, researchers looked at the working environment for women and the challenges they encounter. The primary goal of research is to examine the psychological difficulties experienced by female employees in Tirupur City's textile factories. Descriptive research was used to complete the project. An arbitrary convenience sample of personnel from several departments was used to pick the participants. The Simple Percentage Analysis and Kruskal Wallis test were used to examine data from a total of 200 people.

Keywords: Women Employees; Psychological Problems; Garment Industry.

I. Introduction

Tirupur is a major player in the garment knitting industry. Tirupur's apparel exporters primarily create and export knitted garments, while woven garment manufacturing and exports are negligible. There is a cluster around Tirupur. It's all done outside the factory in units such as knitting and dyeing and bleaching units; fabric printing; garments embroidered; compacting and calendaring; and other ancillary units. The textile industry in Tirupur faces numerous difficulties, including a lack of adequate road and other transportation infrastructure, a labor shortage during peak season, outdated equipment, pollution, exchange rate fluctuations, cotton yarn price fluctuations, and reliance on cotton that is out of control. Workforce development and other novel approaches should be a priority for the Indian government to boost export marketing activities among India's garment exporters.

In addition to the cities listed above, Ludhiana, Delhi, Kolkata, and Mumbai produce knitted clothing in India. Additionally, this industry is known as the hosiery clothing sector, the knitted clothing apparel industry, and the knitted clothing industry. Tirupur is the seventh-largest town in Tamil Nadu and is located 60 kilometers from Coimbatore, known as the

“Manchester of the South,” in southern India. Avinashi, Nallur, Mangalam, Kangeyam, Palladam, and Koduwai, all within a 15-kilometer radius of the city, have contributed to its growth. Group, Other nearby locations (cities) known for their contributions to the textile industry includes Tirupur, popularly known as knitwear city, Banian city, Kutti (little) Japan, and Dollar city. Eighty kilometers east of Tirupur lies the town of Karur. Textiles for house furnishings are famous in Karur. Nearby Tirupur, Erode is known for its Lungi (Dotty).

Nearby cities Chennim and Bhavani, both in the Tirupur district of Tamil Nadu, are known for their handwoven bed linens. Carpet city is the local nickname. Among the city’s most well-known exports are its machine tools and pumps and yarns and fabrics of many types and colors. Tirupur’s clothing industry is primarily a small-scale business, with many of the companies being small exporters. The Tirupur exporters focus on the low-volume mid-fashion category, especially the women’s and women’s wear components.

II. Significance of the Study

This study could provide an employee perception of problems and prospects in the garment industry in context to the Tirupur. The employee was concerned about external influencing factors, influential internal factors, the intervention of local people, and responsible garment. Targeted population of this study is employees of the Tirupur working in garment units. This study also focuses on the probability of the positive relationship between Responsible Garment and External Factors, Responsible Garment and Internal Factors, Responsible Garment, and Intervention of Local People. It is also to be studied that the level of employees’ perceptions on other relevant factors is evaluated from the literature review. This study may be helpful to the entities or persons associated with the garment industry as a problem-solving tool. It may be beneficial to academicians, researchers as well as professionals.

III. Statement of the Problem

With a focus on the apparel business, this research makes good use of women’s rights. This is a good fit in Tirupur, where women make up a large workforce. To that end, we’re conducting this research in Tirupur’s garment sector to learn more about the status of women workers, the resources they have access to, and the issues they confront on the job.

The garment industry is plagued by several well-known issues, including fire safety, exposure to chemicals and inadequate infrastructure, highly controlled, stressful, and repetitive work environments, irregular work volume and schedules, lack of access to benefits like medical insurance and maternity leave, and instances of workplace-based harassment, violence, and discrimination. Even though both sexes face the same obstacles, women employees are more in danger than males. It’s not just that women make up many low-skilled, low-wage jobs; they’re also subjected to oppressive social norms and power relations. On the other hand, women face discrimination whether they decide to start a family or already do so. Candidates

in some textile companies are questioned if they are married or planning a family while applying for jobs.

In this connection, the present study focuses on “Psychological Problems Faced by Women Employees in Garment Companies in Tirupur City” carried out by employers in various dimensions of influential external and internal factors. The voice of local people in garment activities carried out by entrepreneurs should also be considered. The researchers argue for redefining the responsible garment activities.

IV. Objective of the Study

The study’s overall objective is to analyze “Psychological Problems Faced by Women Employees in Garment Companies in Tirupur City.”

The main objectives of the study are:

1. To analyze the demographic profile of the selected women employees working in the garments industry in Tirupur City.
2. To identify the women employees’ psychological problems working in the garment industry in the study area.
3. To suggest better ways to improve the facilities and welfare measures for women employees in the garment industry.

V. Hypothesis of the Study

H₀: There is no association between psychological problems faced by women employees in garments companies and the mean rank of demographic factors of the respondents

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND RESEARCH DESIGN

6.1 Sampling Technique

It was decided to employ a sampling method that did not involve probability; however other methods were briefly examined. Researchers employ statistical sampling techniques as part of the sampling process. When researchers want to get a complete picture of a population after conducting a small sampling, they use this method. A representative sample must be used for gathering data. Statistical total relies heavily on responsiveness to prove a complete picture of the population online. What if the piece isn’t representative of the population as a whole? If the model results are tested on a representative sample of the people, the conclusions drawn from those results will differ from those drawn from a more extensive selection.

Statistical sampling techniques allow researchers to estimate the number of subjects that can be included in a study sample as well as the type of sampling technique, length of study, quantity and quality and quantity of materials used, ethical concerns, availability of subjects and samples, the need for a survey and the number of people needed to conduct the study. The sampling method in which models are chosen because they are easily accessible rather than because they are assumed to represent the population. It is the case unless random or representative sampling is used. Using this sampling technique, researchers can use whatever they choose from the research outline. The model is selected depending on the preferences of the respondents and the ease with which they can be sampled. This type of sampling is less time-consuming and less costly to carry out. Even though convenience sampling can handle a large amount of data, it cannot accurately reflect the population.

6.2 Statistical Tools

It was decided to use tables to present the findings derived from the primary data received from the survey participants. This study's statistical tests used a 5% and 1% significance threshold. Simple Percentage Analysis and the Kruskal-Wallis test are two of the statistical tests employed in this investigation.

VII. Limitations of the Study

Any research has its limitations and general limitations. There are following limitations are recorded during the investigation.

1. This academic study has limitations like time constraints and funding issues for data collection and complete fieldwork.
2. The data collection was confined to only four factors: external factors, internal factors, the intervention of local people, and responsible garment. These factors can be extended to expanded objectives.
3. The area of the target population was the Tirupur Region.
4. The results of data analysis cannot generalize to all the regions of Tirupur because all areas do not have the same problems.

VIII. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Research starts with a review of the existing literature. It reduces the risk of duplication of effort and expands the scope of the study question. Psychological issues faced by women employed in the garment industry in Tirupur City have been studied extensively in India and other nations across the world. Many diverse facets of the garment business are addressed in these studies, including labor challenges, government policies, and environmental concerns.

To better understand the previous research on the same topic, it is necessary to look at previous studies. Finding relevant articles and studies in the field is essential since it gives us a sense of focusing our efforts. The researcher has been trying to emphasize the importance of reading relevant literature.

There are several academicians as well as researchers who review the prior research in each given study. According to a few examples: -

Workers' lives, especially those of women and their families, were the focus of Satrya et al. (2017). Based on a focus group discussion, the research methodology used in this study is qualitative research. Indonesian garment factories are divided into factories that have previously participated in Indonesian better-to-work programs (BWI factories) and factories that have not yet participated in better-to-work programs (Non-BWI factories). In this investigation, working conditions and individual circumstances are the two axes of consideration. As a result, the BWI factories have better working conditions and emotional dimensions than the non-BWI factories regarding compensation, giving birth, safety work, supervisor connection, corporate regulations, and promotion.

Female employees in Bangladesh's ready-to-wear business are more likely to be promoted if they are empowered, flexible, and trusted, according to a study published in 2018. When it comes to advancing women in the workplace, empowerment and confidence are vital, but flexibility has less impact. An additional goal of the research was to determine which of three characteristics is most critical for women's advancement in the readymade garment industry's upper management ranks and levels of responsibility. Empowerment and trust have been determined to be more important than flexibility. When women in the workplace are empowered and trusted, they are more likely to rise through the ranks, as evidenced by the findings. Though, owing to the nature of the job and the operational processes, flexibility may not be acceptable or viable in the context of Bangladesh's RMG business. The policymakers in Bangladesh's RMG business should, it is urged, guarantee that women are more empowered and trusted to access senior positions. RMG organizations can begin to plan how to bring women with experience, qualifications, and skills to the upper echelons of their organizations. According to Kabir et al. (2018), the readymade garment business in Bangladesh substantially impacts employment. Women can now work and contribute to their own and family's security.

Consequently, the traditional and cultural conventions, such as male bread-earners and female bread-eaters, are being re-evaluated. It can be argued that women have achieved economic independence. Despite these achievements for women, factory owners place their profits above the well-being of their workforce. Work-related health care, reasonable working hours, and fair compensation are the three most critical intellectual regions that contribute to the quality of work-life, according to Kumar (2018). The dynamic working environment provided by the great and safe working environment is a source for the women employees. A health risk should not be associated with the work performed by female garment workers.

Individuals at the top and lower echelons of management who are aware of the challenges, dangers, and rights guaranteed to them as human beings can accomplish a great deal via open and honest discussion. The quality of work-life of a considerable portion of women workers who perform at their best is a significant problem for the world's nations. But it also goes for appealing efficiency, flexibility, and sufficient overall success of firms. This issue accomplishes more vital employee fulfillment.

Mahmud et al. (2018) investigated Bangladeshi female garment workers' mental and physical health. Occupational hazards are exacerbated by low socioeconomic status, sedentary labor, exposure to hazardous materials, and long hours. To protect workers' health, the study advises flexible working conditions. It's also critical to have a well-equipped medical facility so workers may receive timely and effective treatment for any health issues. Whenever a situation at the factory could potentially endanger a worker's health, the factory management should act immediately. Government officials should cooperate with trade groups like BGMEA (Bangladesh Garment Manufacturers and Exporters Association) and purchasers to improve Bangladesh's garment industry's workplace health management.

Using Rachel and Priya's (2018) research, we examined how women operate in their workplaces regarding the workplace facilities they have access to, such as crèche facilities, ventilation facilities, financial benefits, and work enrichment possibilities. Main aim of research was to examine the rights of female workers in the Tirupur garment sector. According to this study, women's lives and careers are profoundly impacted by juggling the demands of work and family as they start their professions. It is a challenge because of the traditional gender roles that still exist in families and the workplace. In this way, some social positions and occupations correlate to the sexes.

Persons of color, people of different ethnic backgrounds, and minorities join them. Once an organization has successfully attracted female employees, they no longer have to answer to anyone. On the other hand, some organizations are free of gender bias and offer equal opportunity for success to men and women.

Ramanjaniah and Somashekher (2018) examined the local influence of developing global retailers' supply chains on the quality of jobs they produce and the power of workers and their organizations in the situations. Surveying Bangalore's readymade garments sector, where clothing production for foreign names is commonplace, was chosen in this case. Employees in outside factories and slums were randomly picked for this survey since management refused to approve an on-factory study. Migration among rural and urban areas has resulted in an adequate workforce supply of about seven and a half million people. They cannot organize or settle because of their socioeconomic disadvantage and gender they are female). They remain helpless in the face of global capital since their decision-making centers are far away, and local authorities cannot reach the workers s. After more than 20 years of rapid expansion, there is no sign of labor market tightness in Bangalore's clothing sector. To begin with, it is challenging to establish unions in an export-driven environment, which is especially true among a weak, unstable, gendered, semi-unskilled population whose flight path between rural hinterlands and cities appears to go on forever.

Suresha (2018) examined the differences in the type and conditions of job and income between men and women. According to their findings, researchers found that having less education and skills translates into poorer working circumstances for women. Women's working conditions are favorable, with fewer advancement, promotion, and occupational safety opportunities than men. Women's issues focus on the study, which aims to identify best practices to help employers and trade unions improve working conditions for women and boost their income.

Khare and Kapoor (2019) set out to determine what influences women's employment and family responsibilities in India's lower socioeconomic strata. The research identifies several characteristics that influence happiness at home and productivity at work, contentment at work, and production at home. Couples with kids find it even more challenging to juggle their job and home lives. In other words, the organization's goal is to identify and address these issues. Working long hours or overtime is one of the most common causes of health problems among employees. Employees' mental health can be jeopardized if they cannot connect with their families. Although they are proud to be the breadwinners of their families, the company must come up with ways to help employees cope with stress because at a macro level, a satisfied employee with a happy home is more likely to contribute positively to nation-building than those who are unhappy, tired, or frustrated with their jobs. Suppose firms are serious about solving this severe problem. In that case, they could implement the "Work-Life Benefits Program," which provides flexible working hours and leave policies, as well as benefits, in place of family care duties. These factors influence workers' behavior and their level of devotion to the company; as a result, everyone balances their job and family life better. Keeping track of and managing employees' workload is critical to achieving work-life balance. Managers must also be aware of other potential obstacles to a healthy work-life balance. The corporation should provide improved recreational facilities and a work atmosphere, counseling, bonuses for overtime, and other incentives to keep employees motivated. The worker's professional development will be added because of this.

It's Kanchana et al. (2020). When it comes to science and technology, today's world is a place where everyone strives to be the best. Modern society has made stress a global phenomenon. Indian women have demonstrated their ability to work hard. There is a long history of fight and independence in the social arena to achieve this level of achievement. Apart from altering conventional roles, they have preserved the home's work culture. Working women face many challenges in their personal and professional lives. As spouses, moms, and breadwinners, women must fulfill their responsibilities. It's a double whammy for working women, who have to juggle two sets of duties. Women's professional roles appear to be a substantial cause of stress in addition to conventional roles for working women.

IX. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data analysis is the process of rearranging, summarising, and synthesizing collected information to derive research conclusions. So, data analysis is an outcome of all that went into designing and planning a study. A questionnaire, an observation sheet, and a test are utilized to gather data in this study. All three devices are the result of research-generated assumptions and questions. Before discussing and evaluating the data obtained, it is essential to explain the criteria and devices used in the data analysis process. This chapter offers interpretations of the facts considering the hypotheses and theories that were previously presented.

9.1 SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC AND ECONOMIC PROFILE OF THE RESPONDENTS

This article focuses on female employees' socioeconomic and demographic characteristics in garments companies. It ensures the validity of the acquired data and offers an accurate depiction of the unit under investigation. The profile gives readers a more excellent idea of the person's upbringing, culture, lifestyle, and other relevant factors determining their professional competence. Age, marital status, educational attainment, years of work experience, monthly income, type of family, number of members, and the garment industry's residential group are only a few of the essential variables examined in this section. Detailed demographic and economic profiles are provided in the following areas.

9.2 SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Percentage analysis is one of the most used statistical strategies for analyzing and interpreting data from primary sources. The percentage of a sample's total replies to a single survey question is the focus of this metric. It is a straightforward method of analyzing research findings, making them accessible to many audiences. It is typically utilized by commercial research firms and is depicted in many diagrams.

9.2.1 AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

The respondents' ages provide background information to the readers. The distribution of respondents' ages in the clothing business is shown in the following table and figure.

It is seen from Table 1 that respondents are classified into three age groups, namely, 18 – 25 years, 26 to 35 years, 36 to 45 years, and above 45 years. It indicates that 5percentcent of respondents below 25 years are in the productivity span of life and have gained more knowledge on the field through experience. The age group between 36 to 45 years accounts for 23.34 percent representing matured employees in the garment business and will be responsible for effectively using work culture and branding. The other age groups of above 45 years for well-experienced women employees who have adequate and rich knowledge

about daily activities accounting for only 13.90 percent. Finally, 26 percent of the women employees are 12. Percent they also youth and double mind stage, because newly got married and expect increments in the workplace. So, they have a little bit of knowledge about the garments field.

9.2.2 MARITAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Two mature people of opposite sex engage in marriage in the Indian context, which regards it as sacred and revered. India's Hindu Marriage Act-1955 and Special Marriage Act, 1954 mandate that the male and female age limit for entering a marriage contract be 21 and 18, respectively. According to marital status, the following table depicts the distribution of the participants.

It is interesting to note from the above-represented table that in the case of textile organizations, many women employees are married (58.93 percent), smaller numbers of women employees are unmarried (41.07 percent), which further shows the employability opportunity available for the fresher or the requirements in the garments industry are at the junior level. There is also a tendency among the younger people in the garment industry to migrate easily.

9.2.3 EDUCATION QUALIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

When it comes to a person's interpersonal interactions, education can significantly impact how they behave. In addition to genetics and upbringing, education has a role in shaping a person's character. Four categories of teaching are used in this study: illiterate, elementary school-level students, high school-level students, and college-level students.

The study investigated facts in that among the women employees of the garments industry, the majorities (41.96 percent) have school level in the study area. However, it is also understood that 23.60 percent of the garment industry women employees are graduates. Another notable observation is that almost 18.49 percent of the women employees are diploma qualifications. Finally, the illiterate of the employees, i.e., 15.94 percent of the respondents are dropout the school studies in the study area. The majority (41.96 percent) has school-level qualifications in the study area.

9.2.4 EXPERIENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents based on their years of service in the organizations. Employment patterns and seniority in the industry enhance the employees' expertise, which may affect the leadership pattern of the employees.

In the case of the garments industry, the great majority, 24.36 percent of the respondents, have experience of 6 to 10 years, 22.07 percent of employees have experience of 16 to 20

years. On the other hand, less than five years of experience and 11 to 15 years are 20.92 percent and 20.28 percent. Finally, 12.37 percent of the respondents are more than 20 years of experience. In the case of the garment sector, most of the employees are younger and have experience of 6 to 10 years.

9.2.5 MONTHLY INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS

Monthly income in the field may play an essential role in determining lifestyle style, work culture, retention, and leadership quality. Table 1 presents the monthly payment and classifies four categories. As evident from Table 1, most of the respondents, 28.83 percent of women employees, draw salaries Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000, 27.68 percent of the employees draw salaries below Rs.5,000 in the garments sector. 26.40 percent of the employees draw salary between Rs.10,001 to Rs.15,000. Lastly, 17.09 percent of the employees draw a salary of above 15,000. It is also evident from the study that some of the women employees of the garment companies are drawing low salaries. Medium-level companies cannot give a good pay package to their employees compared to higher-level companies. In the present global economic scenario, most garments industries are reducing either the salary package of their employees or the number of employees. It reflects that the higher rank possession of the women employees only draws above Rs.25,000.

9.2.6 NATURE OF FAMILY OF THE RESPONDENTS

The nature of the family is crucial central contact on working conditions of women employees because the joint family women have more commitment than nuclear family women. Concurrently, the growing number of dependents naturally grows the necessity to earn more for the family. For this purpose of the study, the nature of the family was classified into two categories.

It is evident from table 1 that 77.30 percent of the respondents are from nuclear families, and 22.70 percent of the respondents are from joint families. In this study, women employees from 'Joint Family' are comparatively fewer in number (22.70 percent).

9.2.7 NUMBER OF MEMBERS IN THE FAMILY

It represents the total number of family members living with the employees. Since the family size of the employees may influence the level of the standard of living, the respondents may affect their level of perception and utilization of employee retention in garments companies. The number of dependents in the present study is confined to 1 to 3 members, 3 to 6 members, and more than six members. Critical tank numbers of dependents in family members are 1 to 3, constituting 41.20 percent. 3 to 6 members of dependents in the family are 35.59 percent. Lastly, 23.21 percent of employees include more than six members. The analysis infers that the dependents in family members 1 to 3 are more percent) than others.

9.2.8 RESIDENTIAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

The residential status of the respondents helps the readers understand the respondents' background. The following table presents the residential status-wise distribution of the respondents in the garments industry. Table 1 show that 57.02 percent of garment company employees have rental houses, and 42.98 percent have their own homes. It indicates a strong presence of rental house employees in the garment sector. It is a common phenomenon in Tamil Nādu that having their own house symbolizes society. A maximum of 57.02 percent of the employees live in rented houses. Among the women employees, owned homes constitute 42.98 percent of the whole. The analysis reveals the importance of the residents of rented houses among the women employees.

9.3 KRUSKAL WALLIS TEST

Psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and mean rank of Demographic factors of the respondents

Using the rank-based nonparametric approach, you can use the Kruskal-Wallis H test to see whether there are statistically significant variations between groups of an independent variable on a continuous or ordinal dependent variable. Compared to the one-way ANOVA, it is regarded as a nonparametric extension of the Mann-Whitney U test to reach more than two independent groups. Kruskal Wallis measures how much each team's rank is different from that of the average team's position across all teams.

9.3.1 AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank corresponds to the shared values of the variables. Here the age group of women employees above 45 years has lower values than the other variables with the mean rank of 65.00. On the other side, 26 to 35 years have larger values than the other variables, with a mean level of 87.25. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, women employees face psychological problems in garment companies according to age.

H₀: There is no association between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of the age of the respondents

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Since the p-value is more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 5% significance level. Hence, there is no association between psychological problems women employees face in garment companies and the mean rank of the age of the respondents.

9.3.2 MARITAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank corresponds to the shared values of the variables. Here, the unmarried women employees have lower values than the other variables, with a mean level of 68.21. In the meantime, the married respondents had larger values than the other variables, with a mean rank of 85.87. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, women employees face psychological problems in garment companies according to marital status.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of the marital status of the respondents

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Given that the p-value is not more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5% significance level and accepted the alternative view. Hence, the researcher concludes there is a significant relationship between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean to rank the respondents' marital status.

9.3.3 EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank corresponds to the shared values of the variables. Here, illiterate women employees have lower values than the other variables, with a mean level of 61.12. Meanwhile, the graduates have larger values than the other variables, with a mean rank of 93.89. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, women employees face psychological problems in garment companies according to educational level.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of the educational level of the respondents

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Given that the p-value is not more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5% significance level. Hence, there is a significant relationship between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of the respondents' educational level.

9.3.4 EXPERIENCE OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank corresponds to the shared values of the variables. Here employees with less than five years of experience have lower values than the other variables with a mean level of 71.00. On the other hand, 16 to 20 years of experience have

larger values than the other variables, with a mean grade of 89.39. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, the psychological problems women employees face in garment companies according to the respondents' experience in the study area.

H₀: There is no significant association between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of experience of the respondents

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Since the p-value is not more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5% significance level. Hence, there is a significant association between psychological problems women employees face in garment companies and the mean rank of experience of the respondents.

9.3.5 MONTHLY INCOME OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank corresponds to the shared values of the variables. Here women employees' monthly income above Rs.15,000 has lower values than the other variables with the mean level of 60.27. Another side the monthly payment of Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000 has larger values than the other variables with a mean grade of 83.98. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, the psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies according to the monthly income of the respondents.

H₀: There is no close relationship between psychological problems women employees face in garment companies and the mean rank of the monthly income of the respondents.

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Since the p-value is not more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5% significance level. Hence, there is a close relationship between psychological problems women employees face in garment companies and the mean rank of the respondents' monthly income.

9.3.6 NATURE OF FAMILY OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank corresponds to the shared values of the variables. Here employees from nuclear families have lower values than the other variables, with a mean level of 76.17. On the other part, women employees from joint families have larger values than the other variables with a mean rank of 95.64. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, the psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies according to the job nature of the respondents.

H₀: There is no association between psychological problems women employees face in garment companies and the mean rank of the residential area of the respondents.

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Since the p-value is more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 5% significance level. Hence, there is no association between the psychological problems women employees face in garment companies and the mean rank of the respondents' job nature.

9.3.7 NUMBER OF MEMBERS IN THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank corresponds to the shared values of the variables. Here employees' dependents in more than six family members have lower values than the other variables with the mean rank of 64.87. On the other hand, one to three family members have larger values than the other variables, with a mean level of 91.82. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, the psychological problems women employees face in garment companies according to the dependents in the family.

H₀: There is no association between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of the number of dependents in family members

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Since the p-value is not more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 5% significance level. Hence, the researcher concludes an association between the psychological problem of women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of several dependents in family members.

9.3.8 RESIDENTIAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENTS

In the Kruskal Wallis test, the values of the variables are ranked for each case. This table lists the ranking of each variable. Low rank shared the shared values of the variables. The employees and own householders have lower values than the other variables with 66.84. In the meantime, the rental householder of the women employees has larger values than the other variables with a mean rank of 87.14. The Kruskal Wallis test determines whether the average ranking differs across variables. Here, employees' psychological problems in IT companies face according to gender.

H₀: There is no association between psychological problems faced by women employees in garment companies and the mean rank of the gender of the respondents

The table lists the result of the Kruskal Wallis test. Since the p-value is not more than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at 5% a level of significance. Hence, there is an association between psychological problems faced by employees in IT companies and the mean rank of the gender of the respondents.

X. Suggestions

The following recommendations are made based on this investigation, which may be helpful to academics and professionals.

1. The majority of the respondents got only Rs.5001 - 10000 as their monthly wage or salary. Due to the rising cost of living wage, it isn't easy to manage their family with their pay. So, the management of Garment Company may consider increasing the wage or pay for their employees.
2. Female coworkers tend to be unaware of their legal obligations. There is a lack of awareness about the importance of providing written employee-characterized wage slips, minimum wages, nondiscrimination of salaries based on gender and equal opportunity for promotion, provision of good working conditions, provident fund facilities, maternity facilities, freedom to form and join the union, treatment with dignity and leave facilities for workers. As a result, female employees need to be aware that their legal employers must offer their employees itemized pay stubs to keep track of their earnings.
3. As a state of employment, employees must be given a documented employment contract or "appointment order."
4. There is no extra compensation for overtime work granted to employees. The management of textile factories must therefore provide overtime pay.
5. Although the company provides a crèche facility, it is not equipped with the necessary provisions. So, they must arrange conditions required in the crèche room. Many women employees felt that a safe workplace is the most important. So, the companies must ensure the workplace is safe for women employees.
6. Proper communication must be established between employees, supervisors, and employers.
7. Paying attention to women employees' complaints and trying to rectify them as much as possible is very important to keep the employees in the organization.
8. Keep a complaint box so that management can be aware of the concerns of female employees and take appropriate measures to address them. The appointment of a female counselor should address the challenges faced by female employees.

XI. Conclusion

Gender equality is a global issue, yet women are not allowed to participate actively in decision-making's social, economic, and political arenas. Women should be encouraged to engage in all levels of management, and this has to change even though women are employed in every area of our selected companies. They are not aware of their entitlements. Consequently, management should use various programs to educate female employees on their rights. In today's fashion industry, a growing number of women are actively employed. However, companies that fail to offer the necessary provisions, such as adequate pay and working conditions, and a proper work environment, exist. As a result, the company's

management should resolve these issues. Women has to be treated equally to men in the work area, and businesses must take steps to prevent harassment, sexual harassment, and other forms of gender-based violence.

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Table 1 - Demographic Profile of the Respondents

S.No	Factors	Classifications	Number of Respondents	Percentage
1	Age	18 – 25 years	76	50.38
		26 – 35 years	19	12.37
		36 – 45 years	35	23.34
		Above 45 years	21	13.90
2	Marital Status	Married	88	58.93
		Unmarried	62	41.07
3	Educational Qualification	Illiterate	24	15.94
		School Level	63	41.96
		Diploma	28	18.49
		Graduates	35	23.60
4	Years of Experience	Less than 5 yrs	31	20.92
		6 – 10 yrs	37	24.36
		11 – 15 yrs	30	20.28
		16 – 20 yrs	33	22.07
		More than 20 yrs	19	12.37
5	Monthly Income	Below Rs.5,000	42	27.68
		Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000	43	28.83
		Rs.10,001 to Rs.15,000	40	26.40
		Above Rs.15,000	26	17.09
6	Nature of Family	Nuclear Family	116	77.30
		Joint Family	34	22.70
7	Number of Members in the Family	1 – 3 members	62	41.20
		3 – 6 members	53	35.59
		More than six members	35	23.21
8	Residential Status	Rented House	86	57.02
		Own House	64	42.98

Sources: Primary Data

Table 2 - Psychological Problems Faced by Women Employees in Garment Industry

S.No	Factors	Classifications	N	Mean Rank	Test Statistics		
					X ²	df	Sig
1	Age	18 – 25 years	76	78.86	5.936	3	0.115
		26 – 35 years	19	87.25			
		36 – 45 years	35	76.03			
		Above 45 years	21	65.00			
2	Marital Status	Married	88	85.87	10.187	1	0.000
		Unmarried	62	68.21			
3	Educational Qualification	Illiterate	24	61.12	12.428	2	0.000
		School Level	63	89.92			
		Diploma	28	86.14			
		Graduates	35	93.89			
4	Years Experience of	Less than 5 yrs	31	71.00	17.926	3	0.000
		6 – 10 yrs	37	75.45			
		11 – 15 yrs	30	86.39			
		16 – 20 yrs	33	89.39			
		More than 20 yrs	19	78.27			
5	Monthly Income	Below Rs.5,000	42	72.12	15.372	3	0.000
		Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000	43	83.98			
		Rs.10,001 to Rs.15,000	40	81.23			
		Above Rs.15,000	26	60.27			
6	Nature of Family	Nuclear Family	116	95.64	4.812	1	0.112
		Joint Family	34	76.17			
7	Number of Members in the Family	1 – 3 members	62	91.82	9.023	2	0.005
		3 – 6 members	53	73.00			
		More than six members	35	64.87			
8	Residential Status	Rented House	86	87.14	9.338	1	0.002
		Own House	64	66.84			

Sources: Primary Data